

DIGITIZATION PROCESSES IN LIBRARIES: PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS

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Abstract. *The article identifies the priority directions of the industry development based on the use of digital technologies in information and library institutions, analyzes their capabilities, and makes suggestions on how to take an important place in the industry by studying, systematizing and generalizing the existing practice of drawing scientifically based conclusions about the introduction of digital technologies.*

Keywords: *information-library, digital technologies, innovative technologies, innovation process, librarian, competence, distance learning, activity, creativity.*

The modern historical stage of development is characterized by the active application of digital technologies to all spheres of human activity. Social processes begin to be subject to the dominant influence of informational values, manifested in changes in legislative policy, economic development and the transformation of the education, science and culture system. Modern society based on wide use of digital technologies is called "information society" in scientific publications.

As stated by the President of our country, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, "To achieve development, it is necessary and compulsory for us to acquire digital knowledge and modern information technologies. This gives us the opportunity to take the shortest path to ascension. After all, information technologies are deeply penetrating all areas of the world today. Of course, we know very well that building a digital economy requires the necessary infrastructure, a lot of money and labor resources. However, no matter how hard it is, if we don't start today, when will we?! Tomorrow will be too late".

In recent years, building an information society has become a strategic goal for many countries. This is reflected in a number of legal documents. An important milestone was the adoption of the "Okinawa Charter of the Global Information Society" by the leaders of the "Big Eight" countries in July 2000 in Okinawa. It is envisaged that all countries should reach a certain level of digitization so that all people can use the knowledge and benefits provided by new information technologies. Their revolutionary impact extends to the way people live, their education and work, and the interaction between government and civil society. ICT has quickly become a vital catalyst in the development of the world economy. They provide opportunities for more effective and creative solutions to economic and social problems for private individuals, firms and communities engaged in entrepreneurial activities. Great opportunities are opening up for all of us".

Technological development has introduced a new concept into the scientific field. Now it is about the development and implementation of digital technologies in society. Their opportunities to effectively solve many professional, economic, social and household problems are unparalleled.

Digital technologies expand opportunities for acquiring professional knowledge, creativity, and getting to know the values of world culture. They give rise to new ways of searching and displaying information. Only those members of the society who have acquired the necessary knowledge that allows them to be targeted in the new information space can make a competent and skillful use of these opportunities.

Thus, digitization is covering all spheres of public life, all sectors, it is thoroughly penetrating the life of every person, influencing his way of thinking and behavior.

Digitization processes taking place in Uzbekistan could not affect such an important social institution as the library. In general, it actively entered the process of building a unified information space and information society.

In the terminology of librarianship, this process was named "library digitization". The history of its development can be started from the 90s of the 20th century, when the technical re-equipment of libraries began. This phrase (although it is controversial) is widely used in publications as well as in regulatory documents. If the analogy of the definition of "digitalization of society" is followed, then under the concept of digitalization of the library, it is necessary to understand the process of creating optimal conditions in them to meet the information needs of citizens, state authorities, local self-government bodies, public associations based on the formation and use of information resources.

The essence of digitization of the library is the use of information technologies to meet the information requirements of its users. Thanks to digitization, library institutions have become modern information centers that give their users access to a vast national and global treasure trove of knowledge.

As stated in the resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on June 7, 2019 "On further improvement of the provision of information and library services to the residents of the Republic of Uzbekistan", in the current conditions of the reform of the socio-economic sphere in the republic, it is necessary that the goals and objectives of the development of information and library activities correspond to the changes taking place in the country and international practice.

Among the main tasks in this resolution, the reform of information and library activities taking into account the development of information and communication technologies and modern global trends; improving the legal framework for the purpose of providing quality social guarantees for the provision of information-library services to the population, and the development of information-library institutions taking into account modern requirements; provision of information-library institutions with qualified specialists have been shown.

In order to ensure the implementation of this resolution, the National Library of Uzbekistan named after Alisher Navoi is implementing the project "National general education electronic library" in cooperation with LG CNS of Korea:

Within the framework of the "National general education electronic library" project, the system of information-library institutions of the Republic has been provided with software in order to transfer it to a single system, In this, the Korean company **FutureNuri** developed and presented the software called **UzNel**, i.e. "Uzbekistan national general education electronic library" on the basis of technical tasks.

The idea of the national general education electronic library (NGEEL) that is being promoted at the moment is aimed at the issues of providing our population with various

literature, legal information and knowledge, providing access to scientific literature, creating an opportunity to use important scientific, scientific-popular, educational literature from any library. The issue of providing scientific literature in the NGEEL project is the fundamental library of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan, the Tashkent University of Information Technologies, the National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek, and the Tashkent State Technical University named after Islam Karimov under the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education. The Republican scientific-pedagogical library is under the responsibility of the Republican scientific medical library of the Ministry of Health. These libraries have the status of <scientific> and form their funds with scientific publications [1].

Purpose and tasks of the instruction: introduction of specialists on the description of articles published in newspapers, magazines, collections in the catalog module created within the framework of the **UzNel** project (NLU web portal and 20 information-library institutions).

When creating bibliographic records through the **UzNel** software, the database is formed in an integral connection with the assembling and cataloging services. It is an important software for the cooperation of the Republic of Karakalpakstan with the regions and large libraries in Tashkent.

Digitization of libraries has a fundamental impact on public consciousness and the worldview of a librarian-specialist, forcing to rethink all the main aspects of professional development. It is not about newly introduced procedures, but about the paradigm of professional activity and education. Therefore, at the level of philosophical generalizations, it is necessary to reconsider the status of the librarian's profession, views on the content of work.

The characteristic feature of the information-librarian's profession today is that the librarian's activity is carried out in connection with three very important areas - information technologies, culture and education.

The profession of a librarian is also characterized by multi-functionality. This leads to a variety of specializations in the librarian profession - bibliographer, cataloger, methodologist, service librarian, etc. Specialists such as librarian-psychologist, librarian-marketer, library design specialist, librarian-sociologist will appear.

In addition, the development of the technical base causes the emergence of new specializations in information-library activities: librarian-technologist, manager of information networks, librarian-web design specialist, librarian-site promotion specialist, virtual reference service bibliographer, etc. All this contributes to the more social orientation of the librarian's profession to the person, to the satisfaction of any information needs of the user. The dynamic process of digitization of libraries requires the formation of new professional requirements for a modern librarian.

We absolutely agree with the opinion of M. Rakhmatullaev that affirms that "practice shows that it is required that humanities specialists (including librarians) who create information resources in the field of culture, science and education and any other field of activity, in addition to in-depth knowledge in a specific field, should have a high level of mastery of information technologies and software in order to solve their professional creative tasks" [2].

Technical and technological modernization of the society has put the acquisition of information technologies in the foreground. In such a situation, if a librarian-specialist performs his activities without using such technologies, the quality of the work performed, regardless of how experienced, qualified he is and other professional achievements, will significantly

decrease. According to B. Ganieva, today a librarian should be "not only a connoisseur of literary and scientific publications, but also an expert in the field of new digital technologies, a navigator of Internet electronic resources" [3].

The influence of digital technologies on the library is extremely wide: almost all the main library processes - collection, processing, service, methodical activities are carried out with the use of information technologies and the Internet. The number of geographical, departmental and other barriers to providing users with open information will be significantly reduced. The tendency to expand the resource base of the library base due to the formation of the electronic resource base of the libraries and the digitization of their personal funds is clearly observed. The information service aims to use the general information resources of society. The volume of information provided on the Internet has grown significantly, which has made navigation and searching for relevant information somewhat more complicated. This problem is partially solved with the help of libraries and library consortia, electronic catalog of corporations. At the same time, the mass distribution of the Internet network complicates the task of assessing the quality, reliability, and authenticity of information[4].

Consumers' demand for information has also changed. The trend of intellectualization of the final information product is clearly visible, that is, not only information about documents, but also analysis of their content is needed. Consumers prefer to deal with secondary information. The use of information technologies allows the librarian-specialist to expand the spectrum of his services, puts a high demand on the qualifications of the staff, as well.

The main condition for adaptation of a modern librarian-specialist to the information society is continuous professional improvement and development. Professional development reflects the process of employees' readiness to perform new production functions, occupy new positions, and solve new tasks.

Professional development and professional retraining of librarians is an important link in professional development. It is they who carry out the activities of adapting the librarian-specialist to fulfill the new job duties related to the use of information technologies.

The role of additional professional library information is also important. It is through professional retraining that new personnel potential of modern libraries is formed.

New technologies are disrupting traditional perceptions of professional development.

Thus, the high level of development of information technologies, the spread of computer equipment is the basis of the modern information society. Information and knowledge will be the main transformative force for the future development of mankind. Active digitization of libraries has led to changes in requirements for professional development of information-library specialists. It took new lines:

- in the substantive aspect: targeting information technologies;
- in the organizational aspect: virtualization, remoteness, age, time and availability barriers decrease.

So what needs to be done to effectively use digital technologies in the library sector?

- Of course, it is necessary to improve the internet infrastructure in our country, improve the quality of services provided by mobile operators, and most importantly, create conditions and privileges for users to master the latest advances in modern information and communication technologies.

- Establishing centers that include structures, media studios, laboratories, etc., equipped with high-performance digital devices.
- Implementation of distance learning process at any time using real-time interactive presentation systems, video-conferencing systems, virtual halls, electronic resources.

The library has fulfilled the role of a social institution that preserves knowledge and guides the world of knowledge, and continues to fulfill its role in this regard. No amount of Internet can replace this role of the library, but even if it is very difficult for development, the focus should be shifted from the funds to the users. We want to say that traditional materials are not going anywhere, but in terms of use, we have given priority to electronic resources, and now we need to improve all of them.

In conclusion, it can be said that the rapid implementation of digital technologies in the library field increases the value of information-technological components in the professional development of librarians. The modern stage of the development of information-library activities requires the understanding of the concepts of "competence" and "information competence" and their wider application to scientific and practical activities. Today's libraries are very different from those of ten years ago and are equipped with computers, tablets and other types of technology. Like other countries of the world, the seven-screen generation of the digital generation - televisions, computers, tablets, phablets, smartphones and smartwatches - is emerging in Uzbekistan. As a result of having such a dense digital environment and constantly interacting with it, it is admirable that today's librarians' thinking and information processing processes are radically different from those of the past.

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